

**AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF ACUTE FISSURE-IN-ANO
(PARIKARTIKA) WITH TRIVRUT TRIPHALA YOG (ORAL
ADMINISTRATION) AND YASHTIMADHU GHRITA (LOCAL
APPLICATION): A CLINICAL SINGLE CASE STUDY**

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ABSTRACT

Parikartika, commonly known as fissure-in-ano, ranks among the prevalent anorectal disorders. Changing lifestyle, increased stress, and disturbed sleep habits contribute to *Agnimandya*, which is considered the root cause of *Parikartika*. Acharya Charaka has described Trivrut Triphala Yog for anorectal disorders in *Charaka Chikitsasthana* 14/66. Trivrut is also described as a *Sukhavirechaka Dravya* in Ayurvedic literature. A 34-year-old male patient presented with a longitudinal ulcer at the 6 o'clock position of the anal verge associated with sharp cutting pain, per rectal bleeding, and severe sphincter spasm. The patient was treated with Trivrut Triphala Yog administered orally along with local application of Yashtimadhu Ghrita. The patient was advised dietary modifications, sitz bath, and lifestyle correction. Significant improvement was observed within 10 days of treatment. Follow-up after two months revealed no recurrence. The present case study demonstrates the efficacy of

Trivrut Triphala Yog and Yashtimadhu Ghrita in acute fissure-in-ano (*Parikartika*).

KEYWORDS: Parikartika, Fissure-in-Ano, Trivrut Triphala Yog, Yashtimadhu Ghrita, Sukhavirechana, Anulomana.

1. INTRODUCTION

In Ayurvedic *Samhitas*, *Parikartika* has been described in different contexts. In *Charaka Samhita* it is described as a complication of *Virechana Vyapad*. In *Sushruta Samhita* it is described under *Basti Vyapad* and in *Kashyapa Samhita* under *Garbhini Vyapad*. Fissure-in-ano is one of the most common and painful anorectal disorders. It is frequently observed in young adults and pregnant women. Severe pain occurs because of injury to the somatic nerve supply of the anal region.

Modern management includes analgesics, antibiotics, laxatives, and ointments as conservative treatment. Surgical interventions such as anal dilatation, sphincterotomy, and fissurectomy are also employed, although they may be associated with complications.

In Ayurveda, Acharya Sushruta described Trivrut Triphala Yog for anorectal disorders and Trivrut as a *Sukhavirechaka Dravya*.

The *Vatashamaka* action of Yashtimadhu Ghrita provides smooth muscle relaxation, thereby reducing pain during defecation. Its *Pittashamaka* and *Vranaropaka* properties help reduce burning sensation and promote healing.

Considering these properties, the present case study was undertaken.

2. CASE REPORT

A 34-year-old male patient presented with:

- Sharp cutting pain before and after defecation for 20 days.
- Per rectal bleeding appearing as streaks on toilet paper and occasionally as drops.
- Hard stool associated with severe pain.
- Pain lasting approximately 3–4 hours after defecation.
- Frequent episodes of bleeding affecting quality of life.
- Longitudinal ulcer measuring 12 mm at the 6 o'clock position.
- Severe sphincter spasm.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Centre

R.A. Podar Ayurved Hospital, Mumbai.

Study Design

Clinical Single Case Study.

Treatment Protocol

1. Trivrut Churna 1 g BID for 15 days with *Koshnajala*.
2. Triphala Churna 3 g BID for 15 days with *Koshnajala*.
3. Yashtimadhu Ghrita 2 ml BID for 15 days for local application in the anal region.

Mode of Action of Drugs

Table 1: Probable Mode of Action of Drugs.

Drug	
Trivrut Churna	<i>Sukhavirechaka, Vatanulomana, Kapha-Pittashamaka</i> , useful in anorectal disorders.
Triphala Churna	Deepana, Pachana, Anulomana, Tridoshashamaka, Vranaropaka. Yashtimadhu Ghrita Vatashamaka, Pittashamaka, Dahashamaka, Vedanasthapana, Shothahara, Vranaropaka.

4. RESULTS

Table 2: Regression of Symptoms During Treatment.

Symptoms	Day 0	Day 3	Day 7	Day 10	2 Months
Sharp Cutting Pain	+++	+	0	0	0
Severity of Pain	+++	+	0	0	0
Pain Duration	2–3 hrs	<1 hr	No Pain	No Pain	No Pain
P/R Bleeding	+++	+	0	0	0
Size of Ulcer	12 mm	7 mm	3 mm	0	0
Sphincter Spasm	+++	+	0	0	0

Figure 1: Clinical progression and healing during treatment and follow-up.

5. DISCUSSION

Hetu

Table 3: Identified Hetu in the Present Case.

<p>Aharaja Hetu Viharaja Hetu Manasika Hetu Bakery products; <i>Ruksha Ahara</i>; <i>Amla-Lavana Ahara</i>; alcohol consumption; low fibre intake; low water intake. <i>Jagarana</i> (late-night sleeping). <i>Chinta</i>; <i>Krodha</i>.</p>

Samprapti

Figure 2: Samprapti of Parikartika.

Pathya

- Fibre-rich diet
- Increased fluid intake
- Buttermilk
- One teaspoon cow ghee before meals
- Avoid late-night sleeping
- Sitz bath twice daily

6. CONCLUSION

Fissure-in-ano requires prolonged healing because constipation and *Agnimandya* repeatedly traumatize the fissure during defecation.

Trivrut Triphala Yog corrects constipation and *Agnimandya*, thereby addressing the root cause of disease. The formulation improves digestion and promotes healing.

Local application of Yashtimadhu Ghrita relaxes the sphincter through its *Vatashamaka* action and accelerates wound healing because of its *Vranaropaka* property.

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